

EVALUATION OF SPECIFIC MARKERS FOR DIAGNOSIS OF PROSTATIC AFFECTIONS IN UNNEUTERED DOGS - A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to evaluate the prostate size in dogs suffering from prostatic diseases using ultrasonography and radiography, and also to evaluate the, canine prostate specific arginine esterase (CPSE), dihydrotestosterone (DHT), testosterone and estradiol (E₂) as potential biomarkers for the diagnosis of prostatic conditions in dogs. The radiographic evaluation of prostate gland revealed increase in the prostatic length and prostatic length to pubic brim–sacral promontory ratio (95%). The prostate volume measured ultrasonographically was 74.38 cm³ and prostate volume/m² of body surface area was found to be 78.78 m² in affected animals. The maximum value of prostate volume was also predicted for a given age and body weight of the animal in present study (37.99cm³) and compared with the maximum value of prostate volume (54.34 cm³) as well as ultrasonographically measured prostate volume (74.39 cm³). The hormonal assay revealed non-significant increase in the concentration of DHT, testosterone, E₂ and estrogen-testosterone. The Protocols for the gene expression study of the CPSE and constitutive gene GAPDH were standardized. The fold expression of the CPSE was found 1.8 times higher than the constitutive gene GAPDH. It is concluded that prostatic conditions affects mostly old age dogs (more than 4 years of age), ultrasonography is the best technique for evaluation of prostate affections in dogs. Prostate volume per unit body surface area shows significant correlation with age and tends to increase with age. Furthermore, the expression of CPSE can be used as a potential marker for the diagnosis of prostatic affections in dogs.

Key words: prostate, prostatic hyperplasia, ultrasonography, prostate specific markers, CPSE.

Introduction

The prostate is an accessory male sex gland covered by fibromuscular capsule, and can be easily identified by the presence of dorsal and ventral sulcus on transrectal palpation. The pathological conditions affecting the prostate are common in dogs and their incidence increases with age.

According to Verstegen (2008), the prostatic conditions may originate from infection, hormonal imbalance or congenital malformations in genital organs, and may be related to a physiological androgen-dependent hyper development of the glandular and stromal tissue. A prostate derived enzyme arginine esterase constitutes more than 90% of the total protein in the seminal plasma and its level reflects the hormonal status of the dog (Slatter, 2003). The growth and secretory function of the gland is dependent on dihydrotestosterone (Tavana and Peighambarzadeh, 2014). In the prostate tissue with pathological changes, a decrease in the percentage of estrogen α in epithelial prostate cells has been reported. The estradiol enhances androgen induced glandular hyperplasia in the canine prostate (Cunha *et al.*, 1983).

Boucif *et al.* (2015) found that clinical symptoms, accompanied with digital rectal examination, can provide a presumptive diagnosis; however, the precise and final diagnosis could be reached only via ultrasonographic assessment. In one study, non- neutered dogs were over-presented with prostate affections, than the neutered ones (Wilson, 2011).

The benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is the most common prostate disease, affecting almost 100% of sexually intact male dogs over 7 years of age, and also the dogs treated with the androgenic hormones (Parry, 2007). It occurs spontaneously as a consequence of ageing and endocrine influence, and may begin at 2-3 years of age, only to become cystic after 4 years of age (Levy *et al.*, 2014). In dogs, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), carnitine and canine prostate-specific arginine esterase (CPSE) are considered as markers for male genital tract diseases (Gobello *et al.*, 2002). According to Chapdelaine *et al.*, (1984), the canine prostate specific arginine esterase (CPSE) is the most reliable marker of prostatic affections in dogs, as it constitutes more than 90% of the proteins in seminal fluid. Prostate specific antigen is not found in serum or seminal plasma of dogs (Dube *et al.*, 1985; Clements, 1989).

Wolf et al. (2012) found that DHT concentration is much higher in the serum of dogs above 4 years of age as compared to those less than 2 years of age. Juniewicz et al. (1990) concluded that CPSE activity was under androgenic control, and could be inhibited by anti-androgen treatment. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the prostate size in dogs suffering from prostatic diseases (BPH, prostatic cyst, prostatic neoplasia) using ultrasound and radiography, and also to evaluate the, canine prostate specific arginine esterase, dihydrotestosterone (DHT), testosterone and estradiol (E₂) as potential biomarkers for the diagnosis of prostatic conditions.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on 19 sexually intact male dogs aged 2 to 13 years and having a history of difficulty in urination and/or defaecation, or both, along with the associated symptoms, such as weight loss, lethargy, tenesmus, dyschezia, penile discharge, hematuria, stranguria, urinary tract infections, urinary incontinence or caudal abdominal pain due to unknown reasons. The animals were divided in to three groups on the basis of their age, as depicted in the Table 1.

This study was carried out in line with the ARRIVE guidelines (Kilkenny *et al.*, 2010). The physical examination included the recording of history and signalment, physical examination, radiographic and sonographic evaluation of prostatic size and evaluation of serum biomarkers

(testosterone, dihydrotestosterone, estradiol, E₂ /T ratio) related to prostate health. The size of prostate gland was determined by using the formula proposed by Atalan *et al.* (1999a), by comparing the measured length of the prostate gland with the distance between the front rim of sacral bone and brim of the pubis. The recording of haematological parameters including hemoglobin (Hb, gm/L), packed cell volume (PCV, L/L), total leucocytic count (TLC, 10⁹/L), differential leucocyte count (DLC, 10⁹/L), was done by using hematology analyzer. The urine samples were analyzed on the same day for physical, microscopic and cytological findings.

Biochemical parameters included hormonal assay of dihydrotestosterone (5 α -DHT), estrogen (E₂), Testosterone (T) and calculation of estrogen-testosterone ratio (E₂/T). The prostate biopsy and gene expression study for canine prostate specific arginine esterase (CPSE) was performed in all 19 animals, with confirmed prostatic enlargement.

The prostate volume was calculated through the sonographic measurements using the below mentioned formula (Wolf *et al.* 2012):

$$\text{Volume (MV)} = \text{Length} \times \text{Width} \times \text{Height} \times 0.523$$

Where, MV (cm³) = Measured volume; Length (cm) = Maximum length (Cranio-caudal dimension) of prostate measured in a longitudinal plane; Height (cm) = Maximum height (Ventral-dorsal dimension) of prostate measured in a longitudinal plane; Width (cm) = Maximum width (lateral to lateral dimension) of prostate measured in a transverse plane

The MV was compared with the normal prostate volume (EV), estimated for a given age (years) and body weight (kg) using the below mentioned formula (Ruel *et al.* 1998):

$$\text{EV} = (0.867 \times \text{BW}) + (1.885 \times \text{A}) + 15.88 \text{ cm}^3$$

Where, EV (cm³) = Estimated volume; BW (kg) = Body weight of the animal; A (years) = Age of the animal

Prostate biopsy

The prostate biopsy was performed in selected animals of clinical group after taking consent from the owners. The biopsy was performed using Ultrasound guided Fine needle aspiration biopsy (US-FNAB), percutaneous Vim-Tru-cut biopsy under ultrasound guidance and excisional biopsy method. Among all the three methods, US-FNAB was found to be simplest and least cumbersome followed by percutaneous Vim-Tru-cut biopsy. The excisional biopsy was found to be the most cumbersome, but resulted in collection of sufficient amount of tissue for further processing in gene expression study.

Quantitative Real-time PCR (q-PCR) for CPSE and GAPDH gene

RNA Isolation: *The RNA was isolated from the stored tissue samples as per the standard protocol. The RNA concentrations of three clinically affected tissues were 415.4 ng/μl, 871 ng/μl and 402.9 ng/μl while the concentration of normal healthy tissue was 168 ng/μl. The purity and quality isolated RNA was checked by agarose gel electrophoresis.*

Complementary DNA (cDNA) Synthesis: *The cDNA was synthesized from the isolated RNA, as per standard protocols using Thermo Scientific cDNA synthesis kit. The synthesized cDNA was verified by PCR using constitutive gene (GAPDH) primers. Two sets of primers were designed namely AG-I and AG-II. The reaction condition for these primers was standardized by normal PCR for optimizing the annealing temperature.*

Further, these reaction conditions were optimized in applied biosystem real-time PCR step-1 system. Melting curve and amplification curve were properly analyzed Fig. 1a and 1b.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 16 (Statistical Program for Social Sciences) software. The values were expressed in mean ± SD. Paired T-test, at a confidence interval of 95%, was used to compare the means.

Results

The prostate disorders are one of the most common complications in middle to old- aged dogs. In the present study, all the dogs having prostatic affections were sexually intact, and 15 out of 19 dogs were more than 4 years of age, representing 78% of the total population. Out of the 78%, most of the animals were between 6.5 to 10 years of age. This finding was in accordance with Olsen *et al.* (1987), who reported that occurrence of prostate diseases were most common in middle to old-aged dogs (Table 2 and Fig. 2).

In the present study, the mean ± SD age at onset of prostate affection was 7.5 years ± 0.70. Labrador retriever dogs were found to have highest occurrence (31.5%) of prostate diseases in the present study, followed by German shepherd and Indian spitz dogs, with 15.7% cases each (Table 2, Fig 2). The most common clinical findings in present study were dysuria, hematuria, constipation, dyschezia, round or flattened stool, inappetance and progressive deterioration of the body condition.

Physical Examination

The mean± SD of rectal temperature, respiratory rate and pulse rate in animals affected with prostatic conditions were presented in Table 04. The mean± SD rectal temperature, respiratory rate and pulse rate in the animals having prostatic affections were found within the normal range. However, individual variations were observed in some animals, in which, there was an elevated rectal temperature, heart rate and respiratory rate.

Hematological Examination

The values of different hematological parameters were presented in Table 04. Most of the affected animals in the present study had a normal hemogram. Some of the animals showed mild leucocytosis and neutrophilia with shift to left.

Urinalysis

The analysis of urine samples was performed in all the animals, and it revealed slight variations in colour, odour, pH, specific gravity and presence of protein and epithelial cells as presented in Table 03.

Radiographic examination

The lateral abdominal survey radiograph was performed in all the animals. Pneumocystography was also performed by pushing the air in the urinary bladder through catheterization in five clinical cases in which survey radiograph was not helpful in revealing the prostate silhouette. The pneumocystogram outlined the prostate gland, and cranial displacement of the neck of the urinary bladder and the dorsal displacement of the colon were clearly evident due to enlarged prostate gland (Fig. 3).

The mean± SD of prostatic length as a proportion of sacral promontory to pubic brim distance was calculated as 97.09 ± 20.27 presented in Table 04. For radiographic assessment of prostatic size, the prostatic length was equated to the distance between the pubic brim and sacral promontory. In present study, the size of prostate gland was determined by estimating the ratio between measured length of the prostate gland and the distance between the front rim of sacral bone and brim of the pubis, ratio was found to be markedly higher than the ratio in healthy animals.

Ultrasonographic Examination

The mean± SD of prostate volume measured ultrasonographically in animals suffering from prostatic affections is given in Table 4. The prostate gland showed non-uniform coarse parenchyma with interspersed hyperechoic and anechoic foci in few cases (Fig. 4a and 4b).

In present study, transabdominal ultrasonography (TAUS) was used for evaluating the prostate gland for its size, echotexture, parenchyma and any other abnormalities in the prostate gland. The prostate parenchyma showed variability in all animals affected with prostatic conditions. It was uniformly homogenous with normal echogenicity in some cases and had increased or decreased echogenicity in other cases. Prostatic dimensions were measured ultrasonographically in longitudinal and transverse sections. Prostatic length and height were measured from longitudinal section and prostatic width was measured in transverse section. Prostatic volume was calculated on the basis of the recorded measurements, using the formula suggested by Ruel *et al.* (1998) and Wolf *et al.* (2012) as presented in Table 04.

Prostatic volume per unit area was calculated to reduce the variation due to body weight. It was observed that prostatic volume was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in prostatic affected dogs than the established values for a normal healthy dog for the corresponding body weight and age Table 04.

Hormonal Assay

The hormonal assay was done for testosterone, estrogen, 5α -dihydrotestosterone in all the animals suffering from prostatic diseases. The mean \pm SD of dihydrotestosterone (ng/ml), testosterone (ng/ml), estrogen (ng/ml), estrogen and testosterone ratio (E_2/T) in clinically affected animals are 0.72 ± 0.27 , 1.03 ± 0.63 , 4.56 ± 18.2 and 0.83 ± 0.64 , respectively as presented in Table 04.

Estimation of the relative expression CPSE gene and GAPDH in Hyperplastic Prostate tissue Vs normal canine tissue: (Pfaffl method)

In present study, the protocol for the q-PCR was standardized for the relative quantification of CPSE gene. For estimating the relative expression of CPSE, the canine blood was taken as the control tissue, assuming it to be comparable with normal prostate tissue. The threshold cycle (C_t) values for GAPDH and CPSE are presented in Table 04.

The canine prostate arginine esterase (CPSE) was evaluated as a potential biomarker for early detection of the prostate diseases in present study. The results suggest that expression of CPSE gene in prostatic tissue was about 1.8 times higher in animals having prostatic affections as compared to the normal animals.

Discussion

The prostate disorders are one of the most common complications in middle to old- aged dogs. In the present study, all the dogs having prostatic affections were sexually intact, and 15 out of 19 dogs were more than 4 years of age, representing 78% of the total population. Out of the 78%, most of the animals were between 6.5 to 10 years of age. This finding was in accordance with Olsen *et al.* (1987), who reported that occurrence of prostate diseases were most common in middle to old-aged dogs.

In the present study, the mean age at onset of prostate affection was 7.5 years and the finding was in accordance with Kraweic and Heflin (1992) and Poliska *et al.* (2016), who reported that the mean age at onset of prostate affection was 8.9 years and 8.2 years respectively.

Labrador retriever dogs were found to have highest occurrence (31.5%) of prostate diseases in the present study, followed by German shepherd and Indian spitz dogs, with 15.7% cases each. This finding was contrary to the report of Kraweic and Heflin (1992), in which Doberman pinscher was the most commonly affected breed. This difference might be due to larger population of Labrador retriever, German shepherd and Indian spitz dogs in Bareilly city of Uttar Pradesh (India) and adjoining areas as compared to the other breeds. Poliska *et al.* (2016) also reported that large dogs are significantly more affected with prostate disorders.

The most common clinical findings in present study were dysuria, hematuria, constipation, dyschezia, round or flattened stool, inappetance and progressive deterioration of the body condition. These findings are in accordance with Johnston *et al.* (2001a) and Maurey-Guenec (2007), who reported that the clinical signs commonly associated with prostatic diseases include,

intermittent preputial discharge mixed with blood, hematuria towards the end of urination, dysuria, constipation, diarrhea, flattened stools and progressive deterioration of the body condition.

The rectal temperature, respiratory rate and pulse rate in the animals having prostatic affections were found within the normal range. However, individual variations were observed in some animals, in which, there was an elevated rectal temperature, heart rate and respiratory rate. This might be due to systemic involvement of the ongoing inflammatory and infectious process. Johnston *et al.* (2001a) and Maurey-Guenec (2007) reported that hyperthermia and progressive deterioration of the body condition were observed only in certain prostatic diseases like prostatic abscess and prostatic cyst.

Most of the affected animals in the present study had a normal hemogram. Some of the animals showed mild leucocytosis and neutrophilia with shift to left. However, contrary to present study, Singh (2009) and Mahajan (2007), have reported anaemia as a major finding in dogs affected with prostate hyperplasia together with leucocytosis. Dorfman and Barsanti (1995b), reported that leucocytosis with left to shift along with neutrophilia indicates acute inflammation of the gland. Similarly, Kustritz and Klausner (2000) also found neutrophilia with a 'left shift' is frequently observed parameter in case of acute prostatitis but does not exclude other diseases. The analysis of urine samples was performed in all the animals, and it revealed slight variations in colour, odour, pH, specific gravity and presence of protein and epithelial cells. The pale yellow to blood tinged colour of urine of the animals is due to enlarged prostate or prostatitis. The microscopic examination of urine revealed normal to mild increase in the number of erythrocytes in urine. The number of epithelial cells ranged from 1-2 to 7-8 per hpf, while pus cells ranged from 2-4 to 17-18 per hpf in most of the cases. The urine culture examination revealed presence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *E. coli* in urine, possibly due to ascending infection from lower urinary tract. These findings are in accordance with Johnston *et al.* (2001a) and Maurey-Guenec (2007).

The pneumo-cystogram outlined the prostate gland, and cranial displacement of the neck of the urinary bladder and the dorsal displacement of the colon were clearly evident due to enlarged prostate gland. The above findings were in accordance with Sharma *et al.* (2015), who reported the feasibility of contrast radiography in determining the prostate size in prostatic affections.

The mean of prostatic length as a proportion of sacral promontory to pubic brim distance was calculated as 97.09 ± 20.27 . For radiographic assessment of prostatic size, the prostatic length was equated to the distance between the pubic brim and sacral promontory. In present study, the size of prostate gland was determined by estimating the ratio between measured length of the prostate gland and the distance between the front rim of sacral bone and brim of the pubis, ratio was found to be markedly higher than the ratio in healthy animals. Similarly, Atalan *et al.* (1999a) also found the higher prostate gland and the distance between the front rim of sacral bone and brim of the pubis ratio in prostatic affected dogs than healthy animals.

The prostate gland showed non-uniform coarse parenchyma with interspersed hyperechoic and anechoic foci in few cases (Fig 4a and 4b). In present study, transabdominal ultrasonography (TAUS) was used for evaluating the prostate gland for its size, echotexture, parenchyma and any other abnormalities in the prostate gland. The prostate parenchyma showed variability in all

animals affected with prostatic conditions. It was uniformly homogenous with normal echogenicity in some cases and had increased or decreased echogenicity in other cases. Similarly, Gunzel-Apel *et al.* (2001) also opined that ultrasonography is a method of choice for the evaluation of size and homogeneity of the parenchyma of the prostate gland. The findings in our study were in accordance with Tavana and Peighambarzadeh (2014) who evaluated the prostate dimensions, shape, lobular pattern and echogenicity of the gland parenchyma by ultrasonography as a method of diagnosis.

Similarly, Levy *et al.* (2009) also found frequent occurrence of prostatic cyst, in association with enlarged prostate, in dogs over 7 years of age and was defined as true cyst in their study.

The findings of present study were also supported by Sirinarumitr *et al.* (2001), who described ultrasonography to be excellent imaging modality in finding small as well as fluid-filled cysts in some cases of benign prostatic hyperplasia. The ultrasonography was found helpful in obtaining the biopsy samples through fine needle aspiration and percutaneous biopsy needle (Vim-Tru-cut biopsy needle). Further, in present study, the therapeutic and surgical interventions for enlarged prostate gland were well planned through ultrasonography. The above findings support the study of Mahajan (2007) and Powe *et al.* (2004) who determined the usefulness of ultrasound guided fine needle aspiration biopsy and other biopsy techniques for the cytological investigation of the prostatic diseases.

Prostatic dimensions were measured ultrasonographically in longitudinal and transverse sections. Prostatic length and height were measured from longitudinal section and prostatic width was measured in transverse section. Prostatic volume was calculated on the basis of the recorded measurements, using the formula suggested by Ruel *et al.* (1998) and Wolf *et al.* (2012). Prostatic volume per unit area was calculated to reduce the variation due to body weight. It was observed that prostatic volume was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in prostatic affected dogs than the established values for a normal healthy dog for the corresponding body weight and age (Table 04). Further, in present study it was observed that prostatic volume per unit body surface area was also significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in all the animals. Similarly, Mantziaras *et al.* (2017) also found the enlarged prostate was the most commonly observed abnormality of the gland.

The hormonal assay was done for testosterone, estrogen, 5α -dihydrotestosterone in all the animals suffering from prostatic diseases. It was observed that hormone concentration was found towards higher side in normal range. The concentration of $17\text{-}\beta$ estradiol in clinically affected animals was found within normal limits as also reported by Mischke *et al.* (2002).

The canine prostate arginine esterase (CPSE) was evaluated as a potential biomarker for early detection of the prostate diseases in present study. The results suggest that expression of CPSE gene in prostatic tissue was about 1.8 times higher in animals having prostatic affections as compared to the normal animals. This observation is in agreement with the earlier findings of Chapdelaine *et al.* (1984), Bell *et al.* (1995), Gobello *et al.* (2002) and Wolf *et al.* (2012). However, the gene expression study for CPSE needs to be further investigated to derive a conclusion regarding the role of canine prostate specific arginine esterase at the mRNA level. The in vitro testing of serum samples for presence of CPSE protein through ELISA might be a simple and non-

invasive procedure for diagnosing prostatic hyperplasia, provided the availability of the assay kit.

Conclusion

It is concluded that prostatic conditions affects mostly old age dogs (more than 4 years of age) with history of difficulty in urination and/or defaecation, or both, along with the associated symptoms. Ultrasonography is the best technique for evaluation of most of the prostate affections in dogs. Prostate volume per unit body surface area shows significant correlation with age and tends to increase with age. Furthermore, the expression of CPSE can be used as a potential marker for the diagnosis of prostatic affections in dogs.

Tables

Table - 1: Age wise distribution of animals affected with prostatic conditions

Groups	Age (years)	No. of Animals
Group A	2-4	4
Group B	4-9	10
Group C	>9	5

Table - 2: Breed wise distribution of animals affected with prostatic affections

Breed	No. Of animals	Type of prostate affection
Labrador Retriever	6	Prostatic cyst, Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Spitz	3	Prostatic cyst, Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
German Shepherd	3	Prostatic cyst, Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Dobermann Pinscher	2	Prostatic cyst, Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Beagle	1	Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Rottweiler	1	Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Bulldog	1	Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Mongrel	1	Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Boxer	1	Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia
Total	19	

Table - 03: Findings of Urinalysis of prostate affected dogs.

S.No	Parameter	Finding
1	Colour	Pale yellow to blood tinged
2	Odour	Normal to offensive
3	pH	Varies from 6.5 to 7.5
4	Specific gravity	1.010 to 1.020
5	Protein, pus cells and epithelial cells	Present

Table - 04: Table showing mean±SD values of different parameters recorded in animals affected with prostatic disease

Physical Examination						
Mean±SD	Rectal Temperature (° F)	Respiratory Rate (Breaths/min)	Pulse Rate (Beats/min)			
	102.4±0.27	35±0.24	86±6.24			
Haemetological Parameters						
Mean±SD	Haemoglobin (g/L)	PCV (L/L)	TLC (10 ⁹ /L)	Differential leucocyte count		
	138.7 ±24.9	0.41±0.07	0.001±0.0	N (10 ⁹ /L)	L (10 ⁹ /L)	M (10 ⁹ /L)
				0.071±0.005	0.023±0.004	0.001±0.001
Radiographic Prostate Size						
Mean±SD	Radiographic prostate size in comparison to sacral promontory- pubic brim distance (%)					
	97.09± 20.27					
Prostate Volume						
Mean±SD	Prostate volume measured as per Wolf <i>et al.</i> (2012) and per unit body surface area					
	Prostate volume (cm ³)			Volume per m ³		
	74.38±60.87			78.78±49.26		
Ultrasonographically measured prostate volume and its maximum predicted value						
Mean±SD	Maximum predicted value (Present Study)			Maximum predicted value (Ruel <i>et al.</i> , 1998)		
	37.99±7.44			54.34±7.08		
Hormonal Assay						

	Dihydrotestosterone (DHT) (ng/ml)	Testosterone (T) (ng/ml)	Estrogen (E ₂) (pg/ml)	E ₂ /T ratio
Mean± SD	0.72±0.27 (p=0.55)	1.03±0.63 (p= 0.07)	4.56±18.21 (p= 0.96)	0.83±0.64 (p= 0.33)
Gene expression study				
Mean threshold value cycle values (Ct- values) for relative quantification of CPSE and GAPDH expression				
Ct value	GADPH		CPSE	
	Prostate	Blood	Prostate	Blood
	30.95	33.78	21.07	26.81
	30.55	34.63	26.03	21.88
	30.86	33.92	20.85	22.00
Mean Ct	30.78	34.11	22.65	23.56

Figures

Fig. 1: (a) Dissociation curve for CPSE (canine prostate specific arginine esterase) gene; (b) Dissociation curve for GAPDH gene

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Fig 2. Breed wise distribution of animals affected with prostatic affections

Fig 3. Pneumocystogram showing, cranial displacement of the bladder by enlarged prostate gland

Fig.4. (a) Ultrasonogram showing the longitudinal section of the enlarged prostate gland with non- uniform coarse parenchyma; (b) Ultrasonogram showing the transverse section of the enlarged prostate gland; lobular differentiation is visible

Fig 4(a)

Fig 4(b)

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